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POSSIBILITY OF CASCADE FLUTTER SUPPRESSION IN FINITE-LENGTH ANNULAR DUCT WITH ACOUSTIC TREATMENT CONTROL ON DUCT WALL

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates the effect of acoustically lined wall upon rotor cascade stability in order to explore the possibility of suppressing cascade flutter by means of acoustic treatment control on duct wall. A three-dimensional model is proposed to predict the unsteady aerodynamic responses of an oscillating rotor in a finite-length annular duct partially lined with acoustic liners. In this model, the aerodynamic couplings of oscillating rotor and acoustic liners are analysed in a strict sense by employing the transfer element method, with unsteady aerodynamic loading distribution on rotor blades predicted by the three-dimensional lifting surface theory and acoustic liners modelled as equivalent monopole sources distributed on duct wall. Moreover, combined with a boundary integral approach, the present model considers implicitly the reflections at duct openings, thus the aerodynamic interactions within such a finite-length duct system can be truly determined. Within the linear scope, the primary perturbations induced by initial cascade oscillation and the scattering fields due to aerodynamic coupling effects are superposed to give the total blade loadings, such that the rotor flutter characteristics can be further evaluated by its unsteady aerodynamic work based on the energy method. Under certain circumstances, numerical experiments reveal noticeable stabilizing or destabilizing impact of both locally and non-locally reacting impedance wall upon rotor cascade stability. And it has been theoretically confirmed that cascade flutter is likely to be suppressed by the proper configurations of a kind of non-locally reacting liner with controllable cavity depth.

INTRODUCTION

Extensive research efforts have been paid to cascade flutter problems in turbomachinery since the middle of last century. However, a brake is on the development of cascade flutter control due to great complexity arising from the fact that any factors affecting the surrounding flow fields or the aeroelastic characteristics of cascade structure are likely to further alter the evolution of such self-excited vibration.

Passive suppression techniques of cascade flutter, which were comprehensively assessed by Bendiksen [1] and have revealed little appreciable breakthroughs in the recent decades, usually come with a limited range of utility under the extreme and variable operating conditions of aero engines. Therefore, active control approaches [2–6] have also been sought. Some attempt to introduce extra perturbations to actively cancel the primary disturbances on the onset of instabilities. However, it is too demanding to accomplish the signal analysis and generate the exact anti-waves during an extremely short time interval in the practical cascade flutter situations. On the other hand, the potential prices of extra weights, aerodynamic losses and shortened fatigue lifetime greatly degrade the desirability of almost all those active control techniques requiring certain electromechanical devices, e.g. piezo-actuators or plasma actuators, embedded on high-speed rotating blades. By contrast, the concept of suppressing cascade flutter with the active control of acoustic treatment on duct wall [4–6] shows a more promising prospective. Zhao and Sun [7] have experimentally achieved the active control of wall acoustic impedance with a kind of perforated liner with adjustable bias flow backed up by a hollow cavity of controllable depth

whose impedance characteristics have been investigated by considerable theoretical and experimental work [8–11]. Then we can expect that, once the in-depth knowledge of the aerodynamic impact of acoustically lined wall upon cascade stability is gained, the corresponding control law of such a liner can be immediately devised for flutter suppression purpose.

Watanabe and Kaji [5] have firstly proven that the change of duct wall impedance could considerably alter the aerodynamic damping of oscillating blades. However, the three-dimensional semi-actuator disk model they used has been excessively simplified. By determining the Green's function for a duct comprised of two parallel infinite flat walls with one of locally reacting impedance, Sun and Kaji [6] further investigated how a non-rigid duct wall can affect cascade stability. Nevertheless, their model cannot take into account the annular effect critical for real compressors or turbines as well as the acoustic liners of finite extent. Besides, a troublesome process involved for numerically computing the complex eigenvalues for soft walled duct considerably reduces its efficiency. Hence, more refined and efficient model is still in urgent demand.

In this paper, we propose a three-dimensional model to predict the unsteady aerodynamic responses of an oscillating rotor in a finite-length annular duct partially lined with acoustic liners. This model is established based on the transfer element method [12,13], in which each segment of a duct is modelled as a transfer element independent of external conditions, whose inner characteristics are totally embodied by the defined multipliers of modal wave coefficients. Combined with a boundary integral approach [14], this method can derive a matrix equation for all the unknown modal wave coefficients from the continuity conditions imposed on every interface of duct segments as well as on inlet and outlet cross-sections. By solving this matrix equation one can simultaneously determine the disturbed fields both inside and outside the duct, with the existing aerodynamic interactions and the reflections at duct openings thoroughly considered. Moreover, two analytical tools have been used to construct the specific transfer elements for rotor and liner, respectively. First of all, by using Namba's three-dimensional lifting surface theory [15], a rotor response function of the unsteady aerodynamic loadings and the corresponding induced disturbances on blade surfaces to the oncoming perturbations can be derived from an upwash integral equation. Secondly, by modelling impedance wall as the equivalent monopole distribution of fluctuating strength, according to the equivalent surface source method firstly developed by Namba and Fukushige [16] for an infinite duct of two parallel walls and then further extended to annular or circular duct lined with finite-length locally and non-locally reacting liners by Wang and Sun [12], the scattering effect of finite-length lined section can be determined but avoiding the necessity for computing complex eigenvalues for soft duct wall. Finally, as indicated by the energy method, the possibility of cascade flutter is evaluated by the total unsteady aerodynamic work exerted on rotor blades, which is obtained by summing up the contributions from both the initial blade oscillation and the

aerodynamic couplings of oscillating rotor, acoustic liners and duct openings.

In the following content, a general framework of transfer element will be derived at first and then its tailored forms for rotor and liner will be discussed subsequently. With the other relevant theoretical tools briefly introduced, the complete process for establishing the present model will be presented. Numerical experiments will be discussed firstly to investigate how a lined wall of locally reacting impedance can influence the unsteady aerodynamic responses of an oscillating rotor cascade, and then to verify the possibility of actively stabilizing a rotor cascade by using a kind of non-locally reacting liner of controllable impedance with its liner cavity depth chosen as the control parameter.

MODEL AND METHOD DESCRIPTION

Model description

Figure 1. Finite-length annular duct in question

In this paper, we consider a subsonic rotor cascade and two acoustically lined sections located on the casing wall in an annular duct of finite axial extent, as shown in Figure 1. The upstream liner is referred to as Liner A and the downstream one is referred to as Liner B. The outer and the inner duct radii are denoted by R_d^* and R_h^* , respectively.

Since of primary concern in this paper is the basic insights, on the onset of instabilities, of the aerodynamic impact of partially lined wall upon the aeroelastic stability of an oscillating rotor in finite-length duct, the analyses have been developed within the linear scope with necessary assumptions made towards flow conditions, cascade geometry and blade vibration modes. Suppose the time mean flow is a uniform axial flow without separation, of static pressure p_0^* , density ρ_0^* and velocity $U^* = Mc_0^*$ (where $M < 1$ is its Mach number and c_0^* is the sound speed). Hereafter, with the asterisk denoting dimensional quantities omitted, all the quantities will be correspondingly scaled with respect to R_d^* , R_d^*/U^* and $\rho_0^*U^{*2}$. Further, consider the unstalled rotor rotating with angular velocity Ω has B identical, equally spaced, zero-thickness blades operating at zero mean incident, whose oscillation in an assumed mode shape gives birth to the incident sources in our problem. All the induced perturbations are small compared to the steady counterparts. Also note that the unsteady aerodynamic loadings exerted on rotor blades have been investigated under fully three-dimensional consideration instead of subject to any simplifications

required by strip theories, while the effect of steady blade loadings has been excluded in the entire discussion.

Method of calculation

The difficulties mainly arise from two respects in predicting unsteady rotor response in a partially lined duct of finite axial extent. Firstly, the disturbances everywhere within a duct are tightly coupled and simultaneously changing, subject to all the scatterings of inner components as well as the reflections at duct open ends. So one cannot truly determine the disturbed fields unless the response function of the entire duct system is constructed as a whole, with all the coupling effects taken into account. Secondly, the capability of treating a wall boundary condition of non-uniform impedance is required, in the preference for a time-saving process. To these ends, we suggest a semi-analytical model developed by using the transfer element method combined with a boundary integral equation, in which the three-dimensional lifting surface theory is adopted as rotor response function while each acoustically lined section is equivalently modelled as a rigid wall with monopole sources of fluctuating strength distributed on it.

A. Transfer element method

In the following contents, a general framework of transfer element will be developed at first and then its specific forms tailored to the inner scattering characteristics of each duct segment in question will be introduced successively.

Figure 2. An arbitrary segment of an annular duct

As depicted in Figure 2, consider an arbitrary finite-length segment of an annular duct, numbered by k . In the cylindrical coordinates (r, φ, z) fixed to the duct, the axial coordinates of its front and the back interfaces are given by z_k and z_{k+1} , respectively. The disturbed fields inside the duct are governed by the inhomogeneous wave equation for uniformly moving medium

$$\nabla^2 p' - \frac{1}{c_0^2} \frac{D_0^2}{Dt} p' = \zeta(\mathbf{x}', \tau) \quad (1)$$

where $D/Dt = \partial/\partial t + U(\partial/\partial z)$, and $\zeta(\mathbf{x}', \tau)$ represents the source distribution. As is mentioned earlier, by treating the acoustic liners on the casing wall as the equivalent monopole source distributions, i.e., as a part of $\zeta(\mathbf{x}', \tau)$, the impermeable boundary condition is imposed on the entire duct wall:

$$\frac{\partial p'}{\partial n} = 0, \text{ for } r = R_d \text{ and } r = R_h \quad (2)$$

Therefore, the Green's functions for duct with entirely hard walls can be consistently applied to the generalized Green's formula [17], which obviates the need to computing complex eigenvalues for soft ducted walls and thus greatly simplifies the solving process for a wall boundary of non-uniform impedance.

Then, it can be demonstrated that all the disturbances existing in the k^{th} segment of the duct can be expanded as the series of modal components:

$$\begin{aligned} p'_{D,k} &= \sum_m \sum_n D_{mn}^k \phi_m(k_{mn} r) e^{im\varphi} e^{i\gamma_{mn}^-(z-z_k)} e^{i\omega t} \\ p'_{A,k} &= \sum_m \sum_n A_{mn}^k \phi_m(k_{mn} r) e^{im\varphi} e^{i\gamma_{mn}^+(z-z_{k+1})} e^{i\omega t} \\ w'_{D,k} &= \sum_m \sum_n V_{mn}^k \frac{\phi_m(k_{mn} r)}{r} e^{im\varphi} e^{i\gamma_{mn}^-(z-z_k)} e^{i\omega t} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

where m denotes the circumferential mode number and n denotes the radial mode number (noting that the lowest radial mode is defined as $n = 1$). k_{mn} and $\phi_m(k_{mn} r)$ are the eigenvalue and the eigenfunction with orthogonality value Γ_{mn} of the mode (m, n) generated in a duct with entirely hard walls. $p'_{D,k}$, $p'_{A,k}$ and $w'_{D,k}$, whose complex modal coefficients are denoted by D_{mn}^k , A_{mn}^k and V_{mn}^k , are acoustic wave propagating downstream, acoustic wave propagating upstream and vortical wave, respectively. We have used the subscripts D and A to indicate respectively the fluctuations propagating downstream and upstream while γ_{mn}^- , γ_{mn}^+ and γ^v denote respectively the axial wave numbers of $p'_{D,k}$, $p'_{A,k}$ and $w'_{D,k}$.

In the first step, we base the discussion on a simplified case. Suppose a forward-propagating wave $p_{A,k}^i$ emanates within the k^{th} duct segment resulted from certain sources. The primary disturbances $p'_{D,k}$, $p'_{A,k}$ and $w'_{D,k}$ transmitting within this segment further arouse the scattering disturbances $p_{D,k}^s$, $p_{A,k}^s$ and $w_{D,k}^s$ due to the aerodynamic interactions with its inner structures. The adjacent segments, denoted by $k-1$ and $k+1$, are assumed to be free from any inner sources or scattering effects. Therefore, the continuity conditions of acoustic pressure, axial sound particle velocity as well as circumferential vortex velocity on the front and the back interface of the k^{th} segment imply

for $z = z_k, R_h < r < R_d$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} p'_{A,k-1} + p'_{D,k-1} &= p'_{A,k} + p'_{D,k} + p_{A,k}^s + p_{A,k}^i \\ u'_{A,k-1} + u'_{D,k-1} &= u'_{A,k} + u'_{D,k} + u_{A,k}^s + u_{A,k}^i \\ w'_{D,k-1} &= w'_{D,k} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (4)$$

for $z = z_{k+1}, R_h < r < R_d$

$$\left. \begin{aligned} p'_{A,k} + p'_{D,k} + p_{D,k}^s &= p'_{A,k+1} + p'_{D,k+1} \\ u'_{A,k} + u'_{D,k} + u_{D,k}^s &= u'_{A,k+1} + u'_{D,k+1} \\ w'_{D,k} + w_{D,k}^s &= w'_{D,k+1} \end{aligned} \right\}$$

It can be proven from the generalized Green's formula that all the scattering waves can also be resolved into the scattering modal components:

$$p'_{X,k} = \sum_{m'} \sum_{\mu} X_{m'\mu}^{s,k}(z) \phi_{m'}(k_{m'\mu} r) e^{im'\varphi} e^{i\omega t} \quad (5)$$

where X can be D , A or V , corresponding to scattering acoustic wave propagating downward, scattering acoustic wave propagating upward and scattering vortex, respectively. And for $X = V$, the left-hand side of Eq. (5) should be $w_{D,k}^s$ instead. Further, the complex coefficient $X_{m'\mu'}^{s,k}$ of an arbitrary scattering mode (m', μ') can be written as a function of the coefficients C_{mn}^k of primary modes (m, n) in the form of

$$X_{m'\mu'}^{s,k}(z) = \sum_m \sum_n \sum_{C=D,A,V} \mathfrak{Z}_{C_{mn}}^{X_{m'\mu'}}(z) C_{mn}^k \quad (6)$$

Later, it will be shown that of primary concern for a transfer element is the ‘‘scattering multiplier $\mathfrak{Z}_{C_{mn}}^{X_{m'\mu'}}$ ’.

It is well-known that the orthogonality of the eigenfunctions of a hard walled duct can transform Eqs. (4) into a series of mode-matching equations. Then, we can further define the multiplier of the unknown primary mode coefficient C_{mn}^k in the related mode-matching equations as the ‘‘transfer multiplier $\wp_{C_{mn}^k}$ ’’. For example, from the continuity of acoustic pressure on the front interface $z = z_k$ we can obtain that

$$\sum_m \sum_n \left\{ \begin{aligned} &(\delta_{m'm} \delta_{n'n}) A_{mn}^{k-1} \\ &+ (\delta_{m'm} \delta_{n'n} e^{i\gamma_{mn}^-(z_k - z_{k-1})}) D_{mn}^{k-1} \\ &+ \wp_{A_{mn}^k}^{p,f} A_{mn}^k + \wp_{D_{mn}^k}^{p,f} D_{mn}^k + \wp_{V_{mn}^k}^{p,f} V_{mn}^k \end{aligned} \right\} = I_{m'n'}^{p,f} \quad (7)$$

where

$$I_{m'n'}^{p,f} = \int_0^{2\pi} \frac{e^{-im'\phi}}{\Gamma_{m'n'}} \int_{R_h}^{R_d} p_{A,k}^i \cdot r \phi_{m'}(k_{m'n'} r) dr d\phi \quad (8)$$

and $\delta_{ij} = 1$ if $i = j$; $\delta_{ij} = 0$ if $i \neq j$. The transfer multipliers in Eq. (7) are given by

$$\begin{aligned} \wp_{A_{mn}^k}^{p,f} &= - \left[\delta_{m'm} \delta_{n'n} e^{i\gamma_{mn}^-(z_k - z_{k+1})} + \mathfrak{Z}_{A_{mn}^k}^{A_{m'n'}}(z_k) \right] \\ \wp_{D_{mn}^k}^{p,f} &= - \left[\delta_{m'm} \delta_{n'n} + \mathfrak{Z}_{D_{mn}^k}^{A_{m'n'}}(z_k) \right] \\ \wp_{V_{mn}^k}^{p,f} &= - \mathfrak{Z}_{V_{mn}^k}^{A_{m'n'}}(z_k) \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

Here, the superscript ‘ p ’ represents ‘pressure’ and ‘ f ’ represents ‘front interface’. In a similar fashion, all the matching equations required on the duct interfaces can be written in a matrix form

$$[\wp] \cdot [C_{mn}] = \mathbf{I} \quad (10)$$

By exempting the adjacent segments and the disturbances generated by the inner sources of the k^{th} segment from the aforementioned simplifications, the submatrix $[\wp^k]$ of the coefficient matrix in Eq. (10), composed of all the transfer multipliers of the unknown modal coefficients C_{mn}^k ($C = A, D$ and V), is defined as a transfer element characterized by generality. Then one can conclude that once the scattering multiplier \mathfrak{Z} embodied the inner scatterings of a segment is determined, the corresponding transfer element can be immediately obtained.

- **transfer element for a hard walled segment**

Intuitively, since disturbances propagate in a hollow rigid duct subject to no scattering effects, the scattering multipliers will vanish when it comes to an empty duct segment with hard walls, thus leading to the simplest form of the corresponding transfer element.

- **transfer element for an oscillating rotor**

According to the three-dimensional lifting surface theory, the scattering multipliers in the transfer element for a rotor cascade enveloped by hard duct walls can be written as follow:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{Z}_{C_{mn}}^{X_{m'\mu'}}(z) &= \int_{R_h}^{R_d} \int_0^{C_a} \Delta p^{C_{mn}}(r', z', \omega) \\ &\cdot K_X(r', r, z - z' | B, C_a, \omega', m', \mu) \cdot dz' dr' \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

where $C/X = D, A$ and V and C_a denotes the axial length of blade chord, which is assumed to be constant along the blade span. The coordinates in the cylindrical frame of reference fixed to the duct of source point and observation point are respectively given by (r', ϕ', z') and (r, ϕ, z) . $\Delta p^{C_{mn}}$ is the unsteady blade loading on rotor blade surface resulted from the primary mode (m, n) of the upwash disturbance ($p_{D,k}^i$, $p_{A,k}^i$ or $w_{D,k}^s$) with the incident frequency ω and the modal coefficient equal to unit. Moreover, the kernel function K_X indeed denotes the mode coefficient $X_{m'\mu'}$ of the scattering disturbances induced by an annular row of pressure dipoles of unit fluctuating amplitude.

The circumferential modes and the angular frequencies of the scattering waves generated at a rotor cascade are proven to be related to the primary disturbances by

$$\begin{aligned} m' &= s'B + m \\ \omega' &= \omega + s'B\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Consider the rotor blades in the present question are all vibrating harmonically with the same annular frequency Ω_s but a constant inter-blade phase angle σ . The inter-blade phase parameter $V_\sigma = \sigma B/2\pi$ can be any arbitrary integer between $-B/2$ and $B/2$, depending on the actual state of the mutual interferences among disk and blades as well as the surrounding flow fields. The blade vibration will then give rise to the primary disturbances in the mode and frequency characteristic of

$$\begin{aligned} m &= sB + V_\sigma \\ \omega &= \Omega_s + m\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

Noting that a lined wall of circumferentially uniform impedance will not alter the circumferential modes and frequencies of an incident wave, based on Eqs. (12), one can further conclude that all the secondary modes generated at the rotor cascade due to the scattering effect should satisfy

$$\begin{aligned} m' &= (s + s')B + V_\sigma \\ \omega' &= \Omega_s + m'\Omega \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

where the harmonic numbers s and s' take the integer values from negative infinity to positive infinite. Then, it can be found that both the primary disturbances and the scattering disturbances generated at the oscillating rotor of concern are comprised of an infinity number of the modal components in a uniform mode and frequency characteristic.

- **transfer element for acoustically lined section**

The application of transfer element method to a finite-length duct segment lined with locally or non-locally reacting liner has been derived in detail in Ref. [12], where Eqs. (22-25) and (46-48) can yield the scattering multipliers for the corresponding transfer element.

So far, all the scattering multipliers of the duct segment involved in the present model have been briefly discussed, and then the relevant transfer elements can be built up with little difficulties.

B. Boundary integral equation

In order to match the disturbed fields inside the duct with the radiation fields outside it, the matching conditions on the duct openings based on the classic Helmholtz integral [14]

$$C(P)p(P) = \int_s \left[\Psi(Q) \frac{\partial G^0(P, Q)}{\partial n} - \frac{\partial \Psi(Q)}{\partial n} G^0(P, Q) \right] \cdot dS(Q) \quad (15)$$

where the velocity potential $\Psi = p' e^{-ik_0 Mz/(1-M^2)}$ ($k_0 = \omega/c_0$) and G^0 is the free-space Green's function, is applied in combination with the transfer element matrix Eq. (10) to construct an overall response function of the duct system in a matrix form. The specific treatments concerning Eq. (15) here are nothing substantially different from those introduced in Ref. [12], apart from that in this case an annular duct is under consideration instead of a circular one.

C. Upwash velocity

As is mentioned earlier, we assume all the blades are vibrating harmonically with a same angular frequency Ω_s , and the blade displacement function $\xi(r', z')$ in this paper is chosen to be exactly the same with Eq. (24) in Ref. [18]:

$$\xi(r, z) = H \cdot C_a \cdot h_\alpha(r) / \sqrt{1 + (\Omega r / U)^2} + \Theta \cdot \theta_\beta(r) \cdot (z - z_e) \cdot \sqrt{1 + (\Omega r / U)^2} \quad (16)$$

where the first term on the right-hand side represents the blade displacement due to the bending vibration of order α while the second term is contributed by the torsion vibration of order β , with their corresponding normalized radial distribution functions being $h_\alpha(r)$ and $\theta_\beta(r)$ and the complex amplitudes being H and Θ , respectively. Note that in this paper, the torsional axis $z = z_e$ is assumed to be located on the mid-chord position.

Taking the blade oscillation in the given manner $\xi(r, z) e^{i\Omega_s t + (j-1)\sigma}$ ($j = 1, \dots, B$) as the disturbance source, the upwash velocity of the disturbances acting on rotor blade surfaces can then be determined by

$$\tilde{\mathbf{u}}_\phi = D \left[\xi(r', z') \cdot e^{i\Omega_s \tau + (j-1)\sigma} \right] / D\tau \quad (17)$$

D. Unsteady aerodynamic work

With Namba's definition [18] of the complex work coefficient

$$C_w = \pi \int_{R_h}^{R_d} \sqrt{1 + \Omega^2 r^2 / U^2} \cdot \int_0^{C_a} \Delta p(r, z) \cdot \bar{\xi}(r, z) \cdot dz dr \quad (18)$$

introduced to the present model, the likelihood of cascade flutter can be predicted by its imaginary part $I_m[C_w]$ (note that the overline represent complex conjugate while $\text{Re}[\cdot]$ and $I_m[\cdot]$ in this paper denote the real and the imaginary part of a complex value, respectively). Indeed, $I_m[C_w]$ is proportional to the unsteady aerodynamic work exerted on rotor blade by surrounding fluids during one period of blade oscillation, thus referred to as the unsteady aerodynamic

work coefficient. According to the energy method, the cascade can maintain stable if $I_m[C_w] < 0$; otherwise, a flutter is expected.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Model validation

Figure 3. Complex work coefficient of an isolated rotor cascade subject to the pure bending vibration

Figure 4. Unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient of an isolated rotor cascade subject to the coupled bending-torsion vibration

For the purpose of predicting accurately the flutter characteristics of a rotor cascade, before any parameter studies are conducted, the validity of the present blade loading response function will be examined. The comparisons are conducted to the aerodynamic coefficients of an isolated oscillating rotor cascades in infinite annular duct defined in Ref. [18]. It can be observed from Figure 3 and Figure 4 that, the predictions for the unsteady aerodynamic blade loadings exerted on the oscillating rotor show in general the satisfactory agreements with those given by Namba [18] both for the pure bending case and for the coupled bending-torsion vibration. Therefore, it can be concluded that the validity of the rotor unsteady blade loading response function has been manifested. Also note that the reliability of the modelling for a finite-length liner as well as the boundary integral approach combined with

the transfer element has been demonstrated in Ref. [12] already. So the present model is believed to be reliable for predicting the unsteady aerodynamic response of an oscillating rotor subject to the effect of partially lined wall in an annular duct with finite extent.

B. Numerical experiments

Based on the duct system depicted by Figure 1, numerical experiments will be discussed in this section to firstly develop the in-depth knowledge of the aerodynamic impact of acoustically lined wall upon the rotor cascade stability, which is assessed by the unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient $I_m[C_w]$. Subsequently, the ability of a kind of non-locally reacting liner with adjustable impedance to actively enhance the aeroelastic stability of oscillating rotor will be theoretically exemplified.

For illustrative purpose, a subsonic rotor cascade subject to the first-order torsion vibration (i.e., $\beta = 1$ and $H = 0$ in Eq. (16)) is considered in this paper. Such a choice is partly due to the recognition that low-order modes are most likely to be encountered in the actual flutters, however, no substantial limitations are set on the scope of blade vibration modes for the present model. The case configurations are given as follow: $R_h = 0.2$ and $R_d = 1$; $M = 0.35$; $\Omega = 2.4744$, $B = 30$, $C_a = 0.2$ and $\Omega_s C_a = 0.5$; the complex amplitude of the torsion vibration $\Theta = e^{i\Phi}$ where $\Phi = 0.17453$ rad ($= -10^\circ$).

Figure 5. Unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient of oscillating rotor for Liner B of a fixed locally reacting impedance

As is shown in Figure 1, five transfer elements should be constructed for the duct system in question. From the inlet to the outlet, they correspond to the inlet segment empty with hard walls, the second segment with Liner A on the casing wall, the third one containing the oscillating rotor, the fourth segment lined with Liner B and the outlet segment empty with hard walls, whose default axial lengths further divided by C_a are $L_{in} = 1$, $L_A = 2$, $L_R = 1$, $L_B = 2$ and $L_{out} = 1$, respectively.

- **aerodynamic impact of locally reacting impedance**

To achieve cascade flutter suppression with the active control of wall acoustic treatment, of fundamental concern is the basic law of the aerodynamic coupling effect between

oscillating rotor and finite-length impedance wall. So in the first step, we focus on the simplified case where the duct walls are entirely rigid except for a section lined with Liner B of a uniform locally reacting impedance (here Liner A has been omitted, so we have $L_{in} = 3.0$ and $L_A = 0$). The specific impedance is denoted by Z_s , which should take a fixed value for a locally reacting liner with settled configurations.

Figure 5 shows the predictions of the rotor's unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient $I_m[C_w]$ for the entire range of the inter-blade phase parameter V_σ . Comparisons are made towards the results for the rigid walled duct and the duct with Liner B of two different locally reacting impedances. Firstly, when the oscillating rotor is enveloped by entirely hard duct walls of finite axial extent, only the mode (0,1) with $V_\sigma = 0$ and the mode (1,1) with $V_\sigma = 1$ are cut-on, and the flutter range is found to be V_σ from 1 to 9. With Liner B of $Z_s = (0.01, -0.36)$ added on the casing wall, a minor increase in the unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient is predicted for the whole range of inter-blade phase angle, most evident for $V_\sigma = 1$. So, under this condition, such a liner turns out to deteriorate the cascade stability. On the other hand, when $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$, noticeable reduction in $I_m[C_w]$ is observed from $V_\sigma = 1$ to 9. Especially for $V_\sigma = 1, 2$ and 9, the unsteady aerodynamic work is reduced to be negative from its positive value under the rigid walled duct condition, which means the stabilizing effect of Liner B with $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$ help to prevent the oscillating rotor from suffering a flutter. More computations indicate that, for a liner with fixed acoustic impedance, the inter-blade phase parameter range of evident influence on the aeroelastic stability of a given oscillating rotor is usually very limited, and the effect is possible to be stabilizing for some inter-blade phase angles but destabilizing in other states.

Then, it is further investigated how the unsteady aerodynamic work varies with the change of the locally reacting impedance. In Figure 6 and Figure 7, the unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient is plotted against the specific reactance variation of Liner B with its resistance held constant as 0.01, 0.10, 0.50, 1.00 and 3.00, respectively. The ranges of locally reacting impedance in these two plots are given to be very broad, out of aeroelastic stability concern rather than any practical acoustic consideration. For the oscillating rotor of concern in the finite-length hard walled duct, the unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient $I_m[C_w] = 0.02071$ with $V_\sigma = 1$. With Liner B added on the casing wall, a critical value of the specific reactance around -2.4 is found in Figure 6. Within a proper range, when the reactance is smaller than the critical value, the rotor which should flutter in the rigid duct can remain stable with the stabilizing effect of Liner B; otherwise, the rotor will flutter and the existence of Liner B may even considerably exaggerate the unbalance of the unsteady aerodynamic blade loading distribution due to blade oscillation. For $V_\sigma = 2$, the rotor is deeply unstable in the finite-length rigid wall, where $I_m[C_w] = 0.2579$. As shown in Figure 7, with Liner B placed on the prescribed section of a small resistance and a favourable specific reactance around -3, the rotor is predicted to be effectively stabilized for $V_\sigma = 2$.

Figure 6. Variation of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ against the change of the locally reacting impedance of Liner B, $V_\sigma = 1$.

Figure 7. Variation of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ against the change of the locally reacting impedance of Liner B, $V_\sigma = 2$.

Moreover, the unsteady aerodynamic responses of the oscillating rotor is found to be very sensitive to the reactance change when the specific resistance is small. When $Z_s = 0.01$, as the reactance varies from -5 to 5, an oscillating curve of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ is observed both in Figure 6 for $V_\sigma = 1$ and in Figure 7 for $V_\sigma = 2$. With the resistance increasing to 0.10, the drastic oscillation of unsteady aerodynamic work against the increase of the reactance is damped a little, while the reactance values corresponding to those peaks appearing in the curves almost remain unchanged. With the resistance further increased up to 0.50, 1.00 and 3.00, the curves of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ become smooth. Moreover, larger the resistance is, weaker the impact of Liner B upon the rotor responses becomes. Therefore, we guess the phase change of disturbances, which is usually more susceptible to reactance than resistance and turns out to be evident only if less disturbances are absorbed on the liner surface, may take a dominant role in the actual effect of the aerodynamic interactions between oscillating rotor and acoustic liner upon cascade stability.

Figure 8. Dependency of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ on the gap between the rotor and Liner B with $Z_s = (0.01, -0.36)$, $V_\sigma = 1$.

Figure 9. Dependency of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ on the axial length of Liner B with $Z_s = (0.01, -0.36)$, $V_\sigma = 1$.

To further investigate the influence of phase shift as well as mode propagation characteristics on this issue, the predictions have also been made by numerically changing the gap between the rotor and Liner B as well as the axial length of Liner B. For the calculations based on the varying gap, an additional rigid walled hollow segment, whose axial length divided by C_a is denoted by G_B , is introduced between the rotor and Liner B with $L_{in} = 3$, $L_A = 0$, $L_R = 1$, $L_B = 2$ and $L_{out} = 1$ kept constant. And when the axial length of Liner B is changed, we still take $L_{in} = 3$, $L_A = 0$, $L_R = 1$ and $L_{out} = 1$. Firstly, for $V_\sigma = 1$ with Liner B of the locally reacting impedance $Z_s = (0.01, -0.36)$, the dependencies of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ upon the gap and the liner length are shown in Figure 8 and Figure 9, where and the results obtained with the duct of both finite axial length and infinite axial length are presented for comparison. In a similar fashion, Figure 10 and Figure 11 show the corresponding results for $V_\sigma = 2$ with $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$.

Figure 10. Dependency of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ on the gap between the rotor and Liner B with $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$, $V_\sigma = 2$.

Figure 11. Dependency of $\text{Im}[C_w]$ on the axial length of Liner B with $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$, $V_\sigma = 2$.

With $V_\sigma = 1$, only the mode (1, 1) is cut-on in the duct with entirely rigid walls. By gradually increasing the gap, the phase of the disturbances incident onto the lined section will change sinusoidally, which justifies the periodicity observed in Figure 8. Besides, the change of the rotor's unsteady aerodynamic work against the increase of the axial length of Liner B also reveals a quasi-sinusoidal pattern, whose periodicity is likely due to the relatively evident effect of the reactance embodied by the phase shift while the small but finite resistance may contribute to its slowly decreasing amplitude.

All the modes generated in the hard walled duct should be cut-off for $V_\sigma = 2$. When the gap between the rotor and Liner B is not too large, the cut-off primary disturbances emitted at the rotor cascade can still arrive at the liner segment and further arouse the scattering waves by interacting with the lined wall. If the scattering fields can significantly alter the primary blade loading distribution, a stabilizing or destabilizing effect will be observed. On the other hand, since all the primary disturbances of cut-off modes will attenuate exponentially on their way to the acoustically lined wall, if the gap between the liner and the

rotor cascade is large enough, the liner cannot affect the rotor responses anymore, which is exactly consistent with the results given in Figure 10. Besides, remarkable quasi-periodic change of the unsteady aerodynamic work against the increase of L_B is observed in Figure 11 with $V_\sigma = 1$ and $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$. One possible reason behind it can be the modification of mode propagation characteristics for a duct containing a large area of soft wall, compared with the duct of the same geometry but with entirely hard walls.

Furthermore, in Figure 8 to Figure 11, remarkable derivations have been observed for all the predictions obtained for a finite-length duct from those obtained for the duct of infinite axial extent. This fact verifies the necessity to take into consideration the reflections at duct openings. Since the unsteady aerodynamic responses of an oscillating rotor in a real engine nacelle must be subject to the mutual interferences of acoustic treatments, duct open ends and cascade structures, providing a boundary condition reflecting the physical essence is then of vital importance for cascade flutter prediction.

- **cascade flutter control by using non-locally reacting liner with adjustable cavity depth**

After discussing in detail how acoustically lined wall will affect the aeroelastic stability of an oscillating rotor, we are ready to investigate the active cascade flutter control with appropriate configurations of acoustic treatments on duct wall.

The acoustic characteristics of a perforated liner with a bias flow through it, backed up by a hollow cavity, has been extensively studied for sound absorption purpose [8–11]. And it has been demonstrated by Hughes and Dowling [9] that the impedance of such a non-locally reacting liner can be controlled by the bias flow rate. Further, Zhao and Sun [7] proposed the impedance control system of this kind of liner in which both the liner cavity depth and the bias flow rate through the perforated plate are adjustable. In the following contents, numerical experiments will be presented to exemplify the possibility of cascade flutter suppression with appropriate configurations of this kind of non-locally reacting liner.

Based on the analyses developed for locally reacting impedance, one can conclude that of fundamental importance to enhance cascade stability with acoustically lined wall is to provide the disturbed fields with a beneficial phase change accompanied by a minor damping, which can be achieved by controlling the reactance within an appropriate range while keeping the resistance small. Since for a non-locally reacting liner, the reactance is highly dependent on the cavity geometry, the cavity depth is chosen as the control parameter for the present investigation, while the specific impedance of the perforated liner with or without bias flow is a direct assignment without loss of generality, rather than computed by using any specific impedance model.

Assume the specific impedance of the perforated plate is $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$ for both Liner A and Liner B in our model. Consider in the duct shown in Figure 1 $L_{in} + L_A = 3.0$, $L_B = 1.0$, $L_B + L_{out} = 3.0$ such that the axial length of the entire duct is a constant equal to $7.0 \cdot C_a$.

As is shown in Figure 12, for $V_\sigma = 2$, with the axial length parameter of Liner B set to be $L_B = 1.0, 1.5, 2.0$ and 2.5 respectively, we try to find the optimal cavity depth of Liner B firstly in the absence of Liner A, i.e. $L_{in} = 3.0$ while $L_A = 0$. As the cavity depth D_B gradually increases from zero, the unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient of the oscillating rotor keeps decreasing rapidly until its local minimum is reached. With the cavity depth further increased, $I_m[C_w]$ will first increase and then decrease. Although for the cavity depth D_B large enough, $I_m[C_w]$ is likely to drop to a value less than its local minimum, the liner with such a big cavity may bring about additional difficulty in the structure design of casing treatment. So we regard the cavity depth corresponding to the local minimum of $I_m[C_w]$ as the optimal one. And it can be found in Figure 12 that, the optimal cavity depth increases with Liner B lengthened, and the corresponding reduction in $I_m[C_w]$ due to the stabilizing effect of Liner B becomes larger and larger. Then for $V_\sigma = 2$, an advantageous configuration of Liner B is adopted with $D_B = 0.048$ and $L_B = 2.5$. The corresponding value of the unsteady aerodynamic work coefficient $I_m[C_w] = 0.105 > 0$, indicating that the effect of Liner B with such configuration alone is insufficient to ensure the cascade stability under this condition. So Liner A is introduced to the duct system subsequently. As is shown in Figure 13, with Liner B of $D_B = 0.048$ and $L_B = 2.5$ placed on the casing wall, for $V_\sigma = 2$, the oscillating rotor which is predicted to flutter in the duct with entirely rigid walls can remain stable by controlling the cavity depth of Liner A within the range $0.027 \leq D_A \leq 0.031$ with $L_A = 2.0$, or $0.045 \leq D_A \leq 0.061$ with $L_A = 2.5$.

Similar cascade flutter control strategies for $V_\sigma = 3$ are given by Figure 14 and Figure 15. Here, we place no emphasis on finding the absolute optimal configurations for the acoustic treatment on duct wall, but a range of the parameter combinations with which the liner system can stabilize an oscillating rotor cascade is in essential demand in the actual control process.

Figure 12. Optimal cavity depth of Liner B with $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$, in the absence of Liner A, $V_\sigma = 2$.

Figure 13. Cascade flutter suppression by controlling the cavity depth of Liner A, with $D_B = 0.048$ and $L_B = 2.5$. $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$ for both Liner A and Liner B. $V_\sigma = 2$.

Figure 14. Optimal cavity depth of Liner B with $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$, in the absence of Liner A, $V_\sigma = 3$.

Figure 15. Cascade flutter suppression by controlling the cavity depth of Liner A, with $D_B = 0.067$ and $L_B = 2.5$. $Z_s = (0.1, -3.0)$ for both Liner A and Liner B. $V_\sigma = 3$.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, a semi-analytical model is developed mainly on the basis of the transfer element method for predicting the unsteady aerodynamic responses of an oscillating rotor in a finite-length annular duct partially lined with acoustic liners.

Acoustic liner of locally reacting impedance has been investigated in the first step to gain necessary insights into the aerodynamic interactions between oscillating rotor and acoustically lined wall. Under certain circumstance, both the stabilizing and the destabilizing effects of the acoustically lined section upon the aeroelastic performance of an oscillating rotor have been observed. In most cases, the impact of a liner turns out to be evident only when its resistance is small, while under such condition, the unsteady aerodynamic responses of the oscillating rotor is found to be very susceptible to the reactance variation.

We infer that the beneficial phase change of the disturbed fields with relatively low sound absorption, corresponding to an appropriate reactance and a relatively small resistance, mainly contributes to the enhancement of cascade stability brought about by a favourable impedance wall. Since the reactance of a non-locally reacting liner is heavily dependent on its cavity geometry, the possibility of cascade flutter suppression has then been theoretically manifested by numerically controlling the cavity depths of two non-locally reacting liners on casing wall within their stabilizing ranges to prevent the oscillating rotor from an amplifying unbalance of aerodynamic blade loading distribution. It has been shown from various numerical experiments that, a case-to-case flutter control law must be devised according to the combined condition of duct geometry, the structural and aerodynamic state of rotor cascade as well as the configurations of acoustic treatment.

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